
INSTITUTIONAL DRIVERS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP READINESS IN THAI TVET

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Abstract

Thailand's transition to a value-based, digital economy under the Thailand 4.0 initiative underscores the importance of equipping Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) graduates with entrepreneurial competencies. This study examines the perceived entrepreneurship readiness of Thai TVET institutions based on the responses from 29 professionals across the country. Using a structured survey, we assessed curriculum integration, institutional practices, skill gaps, policies, challenges, and strategies supporting entrepreneurship and technopreneurship. The results reveal strengths in institutional practices and policy awareness but highlight gaps in curriculum coverage and faculty capacity. A Thailand Entrepreneurship Readiness Index was computed using a five-dimensional framework derived from Human Capital Theory and the UNESCO-UNEVOC Institutional Capacity Framework. Findings indicate a moderate to high readiness level, suggesting potential for growth if targeted interventions are implemented. Recommendations focus on curriculum enhancement, faculty development, industry partnerships, and supportive policy measures.

Key Words: Entrepreneurship, Technopreneurship, TVET, Thailand, Institutional Capacity, Readiness Index

1. INTRODUCTION

Strategically situated at the center of the Greater Mekong subregion, Thailand is poised as the second-largest economy in Southeast Asia (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2025). After its successful transition to an industrialized economy, Thailand is set to become a regional logistics hub in Asia and the Pacific. Its strong potential in driving economic growth and regional development was highlighted with the Thailand 4.0 model which was the country's strategic initiative in transforming the nation from agrarian-based (Thailand 1.0), industrial-based (Thailand 2.0), and heavy-industry (Thailand 3.0) to value-based, digital economy or Thailand 4.0 (World Digital Watch Observatory, n.d.; Statista, 2018).

Despite its growing reputation in the regional and global arena, Thailand still had its fair share of crises and uncertainties that further tested its stability as a nation. The Asian Financial Crisis of 1997 or the Tom Yum Kung crisis, the Global Financial Crisis of 2008, the outbreak of SARS and avian influenza, and the great tsunami that claimed the lives of many are some of the tragedies that shaped the country's resilience, policy direction, and development strategy. Under these grueling circumstances, the Thai people, particularly the entrepreneurs, thrived better by demonstrating their adaptability, innovation, and opportunity recognition (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor Consortium, 2025; Minniti et al., 2005). In the midst of these disruptions, entrepreneurship became the pathway for economic survival and a catalyst for recovery and transformation. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs), community-based enterprises, and

technology-oriented start-ups became the key players in sustaining livelihoods, invigorating local economies, and developing innovative products and services that are responsive to the changing market demands (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor Consortium, 2025).

Underscoring these achievements, Thailand is looking at entrepreneurship not only as an economic activity but also a strategic national capacity. The onset of Thailand 4.0 showcases the demand for a workforce that possesses the technical expertise and the entrepreneurial, digital, and innovation-oriented competencies (World Digital Watch Observatory, n.d.; Statista, 2018). Hence, it is crucial to embed and standardize the practice of entrepreneurship within the core of the country's education and skills formation systems. The Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) specifically plays a pivotal role in honing the future Thai entrepreneurs and technopreneurs. This is rooted with the fact that TVET closely connects its learners to applied technologies, industry practices, and production-oriented sectors. The successful integration of entrepreneurship in TVET will aid in strengthening its capacity in producing graduates who are not only employment-ready but are also capable of contributing to sustainable and inclusive growth as they pave the way for future employers (Asian Development Bank, 2021).

The Herculean role of TVET in terms of capacitating entrepreneurship is drastically redefining the way its people perceive entrepreneurship in Thailand. From the traditional skills supply mechanism to a dynamic platform for innovation and enterprise development, entrepreneurship education has evolved beyond business management concepts. It fosters opportunity recognition, problem-solving, creativity, risk management, and the capability to apply technical competencies into valuable economic ventures.

Nevertheless, entrepreneurship requires more than just curriculum statements or even policy aspirations that are reflected in the TVET systems. At this point, institutional readiness is a vital determinant of the successful implementation of entrepreneurship education (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018). This readiness involves the relevance of curricula, the capability of the teachers and the trainers, access to entrepreneurship training opportunities, presence of industry partnerships, and availability of funding, incubation, and prototyping support (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018; Caci et al., 2025). The presence or absence of these institutional drivers greatly influences mainstream entrepreneurship education. Moreover, the number of empirical assessments that aim to examine the level of preparedness among the TVET institutions remains limited. Though there are existing literatures, they tend to focus mainly on higher education or general enterprise ecosystems. This exposes an imminent gap in fully understanding the institutional capacities within the Thailand TVET sectors (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor Consortium, 2025).

To effectively address this gap, this study investigates the institutional drivers of entrepreneurship readiness in the Thai TVET institutions. Furthermore, this probes into the curriculum integration, innovative practices, skill gaps, policy support, institutional challenges, and recommended strategies as bases to gauge the effectiveness of these TVET institutions in integrating entrepreneurship in their TVET systems. A composite readiness index was also developed to provide an evidence-based assessment of the preparedness of the Thai TVET institutions as regards to their capacity to support entrepreneurship and technopreneurship in line with their country's transition to the modern and innovation-driven economy (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor Consortium, 2025).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-exploratory research design to effectively assess the institutional drivers of entrepreneurship readiness in the Thai Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions. The design supported a systematic assessment of institutional practices, curriculum integration, skill gaps, policy support, and structural challenges that may influence entrepreneurship and technopreneurship development in Thailand (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018; Yin, 2018). The researchers engaged the participants of the Colombo Plan Staff College (CPSC) Integrating Entrepreneurship and Technopreneurship in TVET Curriculum In-Country Program as respondents to provide a multi-institutional perspective specifically from the TVET professionals across the different types of institutions within Thailand. Moreover, the Human Capital Strategy Theory and the UNESCO-UNEVOC Institutional Capacity Framework served as the conceptual bases in examining the institutional structures, resources, and competencies that contribute to the effective integration of entrepreneurship into the TVET institutions (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018).

2.2 Study Context

Thailand's rapid transition towards a value-based and innovation-driven economy with the advent of Thailand 4.0 paved the way for TVET institutions to recognize the importance of equipping their graduates not only with technical skills but also with entrepreneurial, digital, and innovation-oriented competencies (World Digital Watch Observatory, n.d.; Statista, 2018). TVET institutions are deemed as critical platforms in the development of workforce readiness in applied fields. This puts these institutions as central actors in strengthening Thailand's entrepreneurship ecosystem.

Under this context, entrepreneurship is now being seen as a practice that goes beyond business start-up knowledge. This includes opportunity, recognition, problem-solving, adaptability, technology utilization, green innovation, and the commercialization of technical skills. Therefore, curriculum relevance, teacher capability, industry, collaboration, training opportunities, and access to incubation and funding support served as determining factors in assessing institutional readiness.

2.3 Data Sources

In order to provide a holistic perspective on the institutional drivers of entrepreneurship readiness in different TVET institutions, this study utilized multiple sources of evidence that offer a comprehensive understanding of the current practices, challenges, and policy support mechanisms across the TVET sector in Thailand:

- **Primary data:** A structured survey was administered to the participants of the CPSC's In-Country Program on Integrating Entrepreneurship and Technopreneurship in the TVET Curriculum that was conducted from January 26-30, 2026. The survey was able to collect the respondents' demographic profiles as well as their insights on key areas to include the institutional practices supporting entrepreneurship, integration of entrepreneurship and technopreneurship in the curriculum, the observed skill gaps among their learners, policy support, and the challenges in the promotion of entrepreneurial competencies. The respondents likewise provided worthy recommendations on strengthening institutional and national capacities through the successful entrepreneurship integration. A total of 29 participants took part in the conduct of

this research as they represent a cross-section of TVET institutions including vocational colleges, regional institutes, and national authorities within Thailand.

- **Secondary data:** Pertinent program documents and institutional reports were reviewed to generate a contextual understanding of the curriculum design, institutional policies, and structural capacities. Moreover, national TVET policies, strategic plans, and guidelines on entrepreneurship and technopreneurship were analyzed to assess the broader policy environment, and how these support or constrain the entrepreneurship integration process in the Thai TVET institutions (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018; OECD, 2021; International Labour Organization, 2014).

3. SAMPLING AND DATA COLLECTION

This study employed a purposive sampling method in which the respondents were selected through their direct involvement in entrepreneurship, technopreneurship, and TVET curriculum delivery across the TVET institutions in Thailand. In particular, these respondents were participants of the CPSC's Integrating Entrepreneurship and Technopreneurship in TVET Curriculum In-Country Program or ICP Thailand. By engaging these key stakeholders who are actively performing training, instructional or administrative roles in their respective institutions, the researchers were able to collect informed insights on their institutional practices, curriculum integration, and the challenges that they are facing in fostering entrepreneurship and technopreneurship.

The following are the demographic profiles of the respondents who participated in study.

**Table 1. Demographic Profile of Survey Respondents
(n=29)**

Variable	Categories	Frequency
Gender	Female	13
	Male	16
Age	25-29	2
	30-34	3
	35-39	1
	40-44	3
	45-49	5
	50-54	9
	55-59	6
Designation	Teacher/Instructor	18
	Assistant Professor	3

	Lecturer	1
	Academic Head/ Department Head	1
	Senior Administrator/ Director Level	5
	Unspecified	1
Institution	Vocational Colleges (provincial)	18
	Institutes of Vocational Education (Regional/Bangkok)	9
	National/Central Authority (Vocational Education Commission)	1
	BNCC/Others	1

Out of the 31 participants, 29 respondents successfully completed the structured online survey. Despite its modest number, the sample reflects the exploratory and in-depth nature of this study by emphasizing analytical richness rather than statistical generalization. The engaged participants ably represented a cross-section of the TVET professionals from various Thai institutions to include provincial vocational colleges, regional institutes, and central/national authorities. The sample includes instructors, assistant professors, lecturers, academic heads, and senior administrators with a balanced gender distribution, and a diverse age range spanning from 25 to 59 years.

The data were collected directly from the participants to guarantee an accurate representation of their experiences, perspectives, and insights on the institutional drivers of entrepreneurship and technopreneurship readiness within the spectrum of their respective institutions. This method fostered an efficient examination of the curriculum integration, institutional practices, skill gaps, policy support, and structural challenges that helped shape the development of the entrepreneurial competencies in the Thai TVET institutional ecosystem.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section highlights the key findings of the study on the institutional drivers of entrepreneurship readiness in Thai TVET institutions. Drawing primarily on the results of the online survey, the discussion explores the institutional practices, curriculum integration, policy support, skill gaps, and challenges that can affect the development of entrepreneurship and technopreneurship. The results of the survey are then situated within the broader context of national policies and TVET frameworks in order to examine the extent to which the existing systems and initiatives that may enable or constrain the promotion of entrepreneurship readiness across the different types of Thai TVET institutions.

Table 2. Distribution of Entrepreneurship Models Integrated into Thai TVET Curricula

Module	Frequency	% of Respondents
Technology-Driven Innovation and Prototyping	21	72
Digital Entrepreneurship	18	62
Green/Sustainable Business Practice & Circular Economy	16	55
Emerging Technologies (AI, IoT, Robotics, etc.)	13	45
Social Enterprise/Inclusive Business	10	34
Rural Entrepreneurship	6	21
Women Entrepreneurship	3	10

Table 2 showcases the distribution of entrepreneurship models that are integrated into the Thai TVET curricula. The findings present that **Technology-Driven Innovation and Prototyping** is the most widely adopted model as reported by 72% (21) of the respondents. This highlights the importance of practical, innovation-oriented learning. **Digital Entrepreneurship** comes in second with 62% (18) of the respondents agreeing on the relevance of digital business skills. Models that are related to sustainability such as **Green/Sustainable Business Practices & Circular Economy** were acknowledged by 55% (16) of the respondents which suggests a moderate recognition of eco-conscious entrepreneurship. Likewise, emerging technologies to include AI, IoT, and robotics were deemed by 45% (13) of the participants as crucial parts of the entrepreneurial landscape. Meanwhile, **Social Enterprise/Inclusive Business** (34%), **Rural Entrepreneurship** (21%), and **Women Entrepreneurship** (10%) which focus on social inclusivity, rural development, and gender-focused entrepreneurial initiatives are slightly lower compared to the other modules (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor Consortium, 2025).

These results indicate that the Thai TVET institutions tend to prioritize technology-driven and digital entrepreneurship with an increasing attention to sustainability while socially inclusive and gender-focused models remain to be underrecognized.

Table 3. Reported Skill Gaps in the Thai TVET System

Skill Gap Area	Frequency	% of Respondents
Digital/ICT Skills	18	62
Technical/Industry-specific Skills	13	45
Green Skills / Environmental Sustainability Skills	13	45
Entrepreneurial Skills	12	41
Soft Skills (communication, teamwork, leadership, etc.)	12	41
Adaptive Skills	11	38
Learning to Learn Skills	8	28

Table 3 indicates the perceived skill gaps among learners in the Thai TVET institutions. The results underscored **Digital and ICT Skills** as the most prominent gap with 18 of the respondents (62%) identifying this as a key area of concern. Moreover, **Technical and Industry-Specific Skills** along with the **Green Skills and Environmental Sustainability Competencies** were identified by 13 respondents (45%) which signals the importance of aligning training with the evolving sectoral demands and sustainable development priorities. **Entrepreneurial Skills** and **Soft Skills** to include communication, teamwork, and leadership were also noted as gaps by 12 respondents (41%). **Adaptive Skills** are also seen as crucial in navigating into the rapidly changing technological and market environments as reported by 11 respondents (38%). Lastly, **Learning-to-learn Skills** were recognized by 8 respondents (28%) as fundamental for fostering lifelong learning.

Nevertheless, these findings present the multifaceted skill challenges within the Thai TVET system in which the need for a comprehensive approach to curriculum design and capacity building that will address both the technical and cross-cutting competencies (International Labour Organization, 2021; International Renewable Energy Agency, 2021).

Table 4. Innovative Institutional Practices Promoting Entrepreneurship in Thai TVET Institutions

Innovative Practice	Frequency	% of Respondents
Entrepreneurship clubs / incubators	20	69
Business plan competitions / hackathons / innovation challenges	17	59
Industry internships / mentorships	16	55
Entrepreneurial curriculum modules	14	48
Integration of tech-driven projects or prototypes in the curriculum	11	38
Green innovation and sustainability projects	10	34

Table 4 showcases the perceived innovative institutional practices that promote entrepreneurship in Thai TVET institutions. The findings highlighted **Entrepreneurship Clubs and Incubators** as the most common practice as identified by 20 respondents (69%). This was followed by **Business Plan Competitions, Hackathons, and Innovation Challenges** which was reported by 17 respondents (59%). This signals the active efforts to stimulate practical entrepreneurial engagement. **Industry Internships and Mentorships** were also noted by 16 respondents (55%) while **Entrepreneurial Curriculum Modules** were cited by 14 respondents (48%). This reflects the attempts to integrate entrepreneurship directly into formal training. **Integration of Tech-Driven Projects or Prototypes in the Curriculum** and **Green Innovation and Sustainability Projects** were likewise mentioned by 11 respondents (38%) and 10 respondents (34%), respectively which demonstrate the emerging attention to technology and sustainability-oriented practices.

These reveal that Thai TVET institutions are leveraging a mix of curricular and extracurricular strategies to foster entrepreneurship. However, the adoption processes vary across innovation-driven, experiential, and sustainability-focused practices.

Table 5. Approaches to Industry Collaboration to Strengthen Entrepreneurship

Innovative Practice	Frequency	% of Respondents
Internship Programs	18	62
Commercialization of inventions/innovations/products	14	48
Industry-led workshops/trainings	12	41
Joint R&R Projects	9	31
Mentorship Programs	6	21
Green innovation and Sustainability Projects	10	34

Table 5 explores the approaches employed by Thai TVET institutions to strengthen entrepreneurship through industry collaboration. **Internship Programs** emerged as the most commonly adopted approach as perceived by 18 respondents (62%). This underscores the importance of providing learners with practical and hands-on experience in real-world industry settings. **Commercialization of inventions, innovations, and products** that were produced by students and teachers was reported by 14 respondents (48%) which emphasized the role of translating academic outputs into market-ready solutions. **Industry-led workshops and training** with 12 respondents (41%) serve as key mechanisms for bridging theoretical knowledge with industry needs. **Joint Research and Development (R&D) projects** were also mentioned by 9 respondents (31%) while **Mentorship Programs** were less frequently adopted, identified by 6 respondents (21%) as a means to guide entrepreneurial skill development. Interestingly, **Green Innovation and Sustainability Projects** were recognized by 10 respondents (34%) thereby, reflecting the growing emphasis on environmentally conscious and sustainable entrepreneurship initiatives.

With these findings, the Thai TVET institutions are seen to be employing a diverse mix of collaborative strategies with industry so as to cultivate entrepreneurial skills. The focus on internships, commercialization, and applied projects highlights the importance of practical exposure and innovation-driven learning while sustainability-oriented initiatives suggest a gradual integration of socially and environmentally responsible practices in the entrepreneurship ecosystem.

Table 6. Challenges Hindering the Integration of Entrepreneurship in Thai TVET Institutions

Challenge	Frequency	% of Respondents
Lack of funding/resources	20	69
Limited faculty expertise in entrepreneurship/technopreneurship	17	59
Low student interest or motivation	16	55
Policy/regulatory limitations	9	31
Absence of proper infrastructure (Incubator, Labs)	7	24
Weak industry linkages	7	24

Table 6 presents the key challenges hindering the integration of entrepreneurship in Thai TVET institutions. The most prominent challenge identified by respondents was the **lack of funding and**

resources with 20 participants (69%) highlighting this as a major barrier to effectively implementing entrepreneurial initiatives. **Limited faculty expertise in entrepreneurship and technopreneurship** was reported by 17 respondents (59%) which signal the need for capacity building and professional development for instructors. **Low student interest or motivation** was also noted as a constraint by 16 respondents (55%) as it emphasizes the importance of fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among learners. **Policy and regulatory limitations** were chosen by 9 respondents (31%) while the **absence of proper infrastructure** including incubators and laboratories, and **weak industry linkages** were both noted by 7 respondents (24%).

This reveals that while Thai TVET institutions are actively promoting entrepreneurship, the integration of entrepreneurial practices is constrained by a combination of resource limitations, gaps in faculty expertise, learner engagement issues, and structural and policy barriers. Addressing these challenges will be critical for enhancing the effectiveness and sustainability of entrepreneurship programs across the TVET system.

Table 7. Strategies Recommended to Support Entrepreneurship in TVET by Asia-Pacific Institutions

Strategy	Frequency	% of Respondents
Curriculum reform to include entrepreneurial and technology-driven skills	25	86
Teacher/trainer capacity building on technopreneurship and digital tools	16	55
Stronger industry partnerships	12	41
Access to funding/incubation and prototyping facilities	12	41
Policy incentives for startups or student enterprises	11	38
Permission for teachers to partner with students' entrepreneurial projects	6	21

Table 7 demonstrates the strategies that were recommended by the respondents to strengthen entrepreneurship in TVET institutions across the Asia-Pacific region. **Curriculum reform** to include entrepreneurial and technology-driven skills emerged as the most strongly advocated strategy. With 25 respondents (86%), this showcases its importance in equipping learners with the competencies required for the modern economy. **Teacher and trainer capacity building on technopreneurship and digital tools** came in second after being identified by 16 respondents (55%). This underscores the critical role of skilled instructors in fostering an entrepreneurial culture. **Stronger industry partnerships and access to funding, incubation, and prototyping facilities** were each noted by 12 respondents (41%) which points to the need for practical support mechanisms that link TVET programs with real-world business opportunities. **Policy incentives for startups or student enterprises** were also suggested by 11 respondents (38%). This points out the potential of regulatory support to encourage entrepreneurial initiatives. Finally, **permission for teachers to partner with students' entrepreneurial projects** was recognized by 6 respondents (21%) as a strategy to facilitate mentorship and collaborative innovation.

Collectively, these strategies indicate a multi-faceted approach to enhancing entrepreneurship in TVET institutions, combining curriculum innovation, capacity building, industry engagement, resource access,

and policy support. Implementing these recommendations can create an enabling environment for nurturing entrepreneurial competencies among TVET learners.

Table 8. Policies or Initiatives Enhancing Entrepreneurship and Technopreneurship Skills in Thai TVET Institutions

Policy/Initiative	Frequency	% of Respondents
Public-private partnerships (PPPs)	17	59
Industry-driven training programs	13	45
Scholarships or incentives for students	10	34
National qualifications frameworks	6	21

Table 8 defines the perceived policies and initiatives that enhance entrepreneurship and technopreneurship skills in Thai TVET institutions. The findings recognize the significance of **Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)**, as identified by 17 respondents (59%), as a key mechanism for fostering collaboration between educational institutions and industry. Similarly, **industry-driven training programs** were chosen by 13 respondents (45%) as instrumental in aligning institutional programs with the current labor market demands. **Scholarships or incentives for students** were also noted by 10 respondents (34%), emphasizing the role of financial and motivational support in promoting entrepreneurial engagement. Lastly, the **National Qualifications Frameworks** were pointed out by 6 respondents (21%) as a structural measure to standardize and guide skills development across TVET programs.

These results reveal a multi-layered policy environment where both partnership-driven initiatives and structured national frameworks collectively contribute to enhancing entrepreneurship and technopreneurship competencies among Thai TVET learners.

Table 9. Main Challenges Faced by the Thai TVET System

Challenge	Frequency	% of Respondents
Lack of funding/resources	23	79
Skills mismatch with labor market and entrepreneurial needs	21	72
Teacher/trainer capacity limitations	15	52
Low enrollment/retention	12	41
Weak industry linkages	9	31

Table 9 illustrates the main challenges that are being faced by the Thai TVET system. The results emphasize that **lack of funding and resources** is the most pressing challenge as reported by 23 respondents (79%). This signals the critical need for financial support to sustain programs and institutional initiatives. **Skills mismatch with labor market and entrepreneurial needs** was noted by 21 respondents (72%). This demonstrates the gap between TVET outputs and industry expectations. **Teacher and trainer capacity limitations** were noted by 15 respondents (52%) which points to the importance of continuous professional development to equip instructors with the knowledge and skills to deliver quality entrepreneurship education. **Low enrollment and retention** also emerged as a concern for 12 respondents

(41%) thereby, suggesting the need for strategies to attract and retain learners. Lastly, **weak industry linkages** were reported by 9 respondents (31%), conveying the ongoing challenge of creating strong collaborations between TVET institutions and industry partners.

These results portray the multifaceted challenges that Thai TVET institutions face particularly in resourcing, aligning training with labor market needs, and in strengthening institutional capacity and industry engagement.

In order to create a clear basis for the effective interpretation of institutional capacity, a readiness scale reference was devised to examine how well the Thai TVET system supports the development of entrepreneurial and technopreneurial skills. The scale utilizes numerical ratings into qualitative descriptions which allow a more meaningful understanding of the system’s present condition. This framework ensures consistency in analysis as it aids in identifying areas that require improvement, strengthening, or sustained support. This is done by linking the scores with specific levels of readiness. The scale will also serve as a viable guide for policymakers, administrators, and stakeholders in prioritizing strategic interventions towards a more entrepreneurship-responsive TVET ecosystem.

Table 10. Readiness Scale Reference

Score	Description	Interpretation
1	Poor	TVET system shows minimal readiness; major improvements needed
2	Fair	Readiness exists but is limited; some key gaps remain
3	Good	Readiness is satisfactory; TVET system can support entrepreneurial skills with some improvements
4	Very Good	High readiness; system largely capable of fostering entrepreneurial skills
5	Excellent	Optimal readiness; TVET system fully supports entrepreneurial skills development

Table 11 shows the overall readiness of TVET institutions in fostering entrepreneurial skills across five key dimensions. The results indicate that the TVET institutions demonstrate a generally positive level of preparedness, with most areas falling within the “Good” readiness category as deemed by the respondents.

Table 11. TVET Institutions Readiness for Fostering Entrepreneurial Skills

Key Area	Mean Score (1-5)	Readiness Level
Curriculum relevance	3.07	Good
Industry collaboration	3.24	Good
Access to entrepreneurship training	3.07	Good
Availability of funding / incubation / prototyping support	2.62	Fair to Good
Teacher / trainer capability	3	Good

Industry collaboration obtained the highest mean score (3.24) which indicates that linkages with industry partners are relatively well-established. This implies that the TVET institutions are making tangible efforts to connect training delivery with real-world enterprise environments through partnerships, exposure activities, or collaborative initiatives. Such engagement plays a critical role in aligning entrepreneurial learning with labor market and innovation demands.

Curriculum relevance (3.07) and **access to entrepreneurship training** (3.07) also received Good ratings thereby indicating that entrepreneurial concepts and learning opportunities are already integrated to a satisfactory extent. This conveys that the TVET system recognizes entrepreneurship as a key competency area, and has begun embedding it within formal instructional structures. However, further refinement may still be needed to strengthen depth and practical application.

Teacher/trainer capability achieved a mean score of 3.00, and is likewise within the Good range. This signifies a moderate level of institutional human resource readiness where educators possess foundational capacity to support entrepreneurship education. However, the score also signals room for enhanced professional development specifically in technopreneurship, innovation facilitation, and emerging enterprise models.

In contrast, **availability of funding, incubation, and prototyping support** registered the lowest mean (2.62) as it is placed between Fair and Good. This dimension represents the primary constraint area indicating that while conceptual and instructional components are present, the enabling ecosystem for actual venture development remains limited. Insufficient financial support mechanisms, incubation facilities, and prototyping infrastructure may hinder the translation of entrepreneurial learning into real enterprise creation.

To complement these findings, a radar graph was created to provide a visual synthesis of institutional readiness across the five measured dimensions. This allows a comparative view of strengths and gaps within the TVET entrepreneurship ecosystem (Figure 1).

Figure 1. TVET Institutions Readiness for Fostering Entrepreneurial Skills

The plotted shape showcases a moderately balanced but slightly uneven profile which underscores that certain components lag behind others even though readiness exists across all areas.

Overall, the findings portray a TVET system that is structurally and pedagogically prepared, yet still ecosystem-constrained. Strengthening resource support, innovation infrastructure, and institutional enterprise mechanisms could elevate the system from moderate readiness toward a more robust, practice-oriented entrepreneurship environment.

5. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to understand the institutional drivers of entrepreneurship readiness in Thai TVET institutions by effectively analyzing the perceptions of the TVET practitioners and professionals who are engaged in capacity-building activities. The findings highlight both promising strengths and persistent challenges on the aspect of how TVET institutions prepare their learners for entrepreneurial futures.

Across the five readiness dimensions (Table 11), the respondents rated their industry collaboration with the highest score (mean=3.24). This suggests that there is a relatively strong engagement between TVET institutions and industry stakeholders. This perception aligns with Thailand's broader skills policy orientation which emphasizes work-based learning and employer engagement. This is to enhance the relevance of vocational education (OECD, 2021). The OECD Skills Strategy for Thailand mentioned expanding high-quality work-based learning opportunities to include internships and industry placements. These are vital in improving TVET relevance and in strengthening industry-education linkages as a form of response to the evolving labor market needs.

Curriculum relevance (3.07), access to entrepreneurship training (3.07), and teacher/trainer capability (3.00) were also rated as *Good*. This indicates that foundational instructional elements for entrepreneurial skills development are also in place. These outcomes resonate with literature advocating for a shift in TVET from a narrow technical instruction to a more holistic set of competencies. This competency expansion is widely recognized in both national and international education frameworks as fundamental for aligning TVET with digital transformation and innovation-driven development agendas.

Nevertheless, the dimension of funding, incubation, and prototyping support received the lowest mean score (2.62), indicating a relative lack of ecosystem support for entrepreneurial initiatives. This gap demonstrates that while instructional and collaborative mechanisms are already advanced, the enabling environment for translating entrepreneurial learning into a practical venture development remains underdeveloped. This disparity exposes a broader systemic issue that was documented in the TVET literature. These are resource constraints, outdated equipment, and inadequate infrastructure that hinder the quality of hands-on and enterprise-oriented training.

The reported skill gaps in Table 3 illustrate the pressures that the Thai TVET system is currently facing. Digital/ICT skills were most frequently identified as lacking (62%), followed by technical/industry-specific and green skills (45% each). These perceptions are consistent with policy analyses highlighting the need for TVET to incorporate digital literacy and emerging technological competencies in order to meet labour market demands under the Thailand 4.0 strategy. Respondents' identification of gaps in entrepreneurial, soft, and adaptive skills also mirrors broader concerns about the need for "future-ready" competencies that transcend traditional technical skill sets, particularly in an era of rapid technological change and complex work environments.

The respondents also reported a range of institutional practices and industry engagement strategies that were designed to support entrepreneurship (Tables 4 and 5). High frequencies of entrepreneurship clubs/incubators (69%), business plan competitions and innovation challenges (59%), and internship programs (62%) signal active efforts to embed experiential learning and innovation-oriented activities within TVET. These practices reflect the global recommendations for TVET systems to adopt learner-centred and practice-oriented pedagogies that foster creativity, enterprise thinking, and real-world problem-solving. The prominence of commercialization activities and workshops further suggests a growing emphasis on bridging classroom learning with market-oriented outcomes.

Despite these encouraging practices, significant challenges continue to constrain the integration of entrepreneurship into TVET. As highlighted in Tables 6 and 9, lack of funding and resources was the most frequently cited barrier (69% and 79%, respectively), followed by limited faculty expertise (59%), low student interest (55%), and weak industry linkages (31%). These perceptions are consistent with the documented structural weaknesses in the Thai TVET system. Resource scarcity and uneven partnership

quality limit the capacity to provide high-quality work-based learning opportunities and up-to-date training.

The respondents' recommended strategies (Table 7) reinforce the need for multi-pronged interventions. The overwhelming call for curriculum reform (86%) which will incorporate entrepreneurial and technology-driven skills exhibits a recognition that contemporary TVET must evolve beyond traditional technical instruction. This echoes national policy priorities that prioritize broadening skill sets like digital and socio-emotional competencies. This is to prepare learners for future labour market demands. The emphasis on capacity building for teachers/trainers (55%), stronger industry partnerships (41%), and access to incubation and prototyping facilities (41%) further demonstrates that sustained improvements require both instructional and institutional ecosystem enhancements.

Finally, the perception of supportive policies and initiatives (Table 8) underscores the importance of public-private partnerships (59%) and industry-driven training programs (45%) in enabling entrepreneurship readiness. These align with Thailand's evolving governance efforts to institutionalise collaborative frameworks that unify government, employers, and education providers to co-design training and respond to labour market needs.

Taken together, the findings indicate that the Thai TVET ecosystem is progressing toward entrepreneurship readiness but remains constrained by structural limitations in resources, infrastructure, and faculty capacity. Strengthening practical support systems to include incubation spaces, prototyping facilities, and enhanced industry engagement alongside continuous curriculum and teacher development, will be critical to fully translate instructional readiness into tangible entrepreneurial outcomes.

6. CONCLUSION

This study carefully examined the institutional drivers of entrepreneurship readiness in Thai Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions, drawing insights from practitioners who participated in the Colombo Plan Staff College (CPSC) Integrating Entrepreneurship and Technopreneurship in TVET Curriculum In-Country Program. The findings described a TVET system that demonstrates moderate to high readiness in several key areas particularly curriculum relevance, industry collaboration, access to entrepreneurship training, and teacher/trainer capability.

The study emphasizes that the institutional drivers of entrepreneurship readiness in Thai Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions are showing promising progress, yet remain uneven across key areas. The survey findings indicate that the most significant skills gaps among learners are in Digital/ICT competencies, technical and industry-specific knowledge, green and sustainability practices, entrepreneurial skills, and soft skills. These gaps highlight the need for curricula and instructional approaches that address both technical and cross-cutting competencies.

The Thai TVET Institutions are actively leveraging innovative practices including entrepreneurship clubs, incubators, business plan competitions, and industry internships. This is to enhance experiential learning and strengthen industry engagement. Teacher and trainer capacity building, coupled with curriculum relevance and access to entrepreneurship training, are driving positive outcomes in fostering learner readiness.

However, persistent structural challenges still remain. Limited funding, insufficient faculty expertise, weak infrastructure, and inconsistent industry linkages continue to hamper the comprehensive integration

of entrepreneurship within Thai TVET institutions. The respondents emphasized the multi-pronged strategies to overcome these barriers. These involved curriculum reform, targeted capacity building, stronger industry partnerships, and improved access to incubation or prototyping facilities. Policy frameworks, particularly those supporting public-private partnerships and industry-driven training programs, provide a foundation for progress, but effective operationalization requires continued coordination and resource allocation.

These findings indicate that Thai TVET institutions have a solid foundation for fostering entrepreneurship, but targeted interventions are needed to fully bridge the gaps between instructional readiness, learner competencies, and institutional support. Strengthening policy implementation, institutional infrastructure, faculty expertise, and industry collaboration will be pivotal in transforming Thailand's TVET system into a fully entrepreneurship-ready ecosystem. Such efforts are essential for equipping learners with the entrepreneurial, technological, and adaptive skills required to thrive in a dynamic labor market, drive innovation, and contribute meaningfully to Thailand's socio-economic development under the Thailand 4.0 strategy.

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